

Voice for Voiceless People - Usage of Local Television Channel for Uplift the Publics in Coastal Karnataka

¹Dr. Parashurama Kamath, ²Sheen Thankalayam, ³Subin Thomas

¹Assistant Professor, ²Research Scholar, ³Research Scholar

^{1,2}Department of Media Studies, ³School of Law,

^{1,2}CHRIST University, Bangalore, India, ³Alliance University, Bangalore, India

Abstract : The role of media as an integral part of human life is very crucial. Modern media world is regarded as “Window to the world”. It is well accepted that mass media has a definite role in the process of social change. The range of the mass media’s involvement in welfare is enormous. But in the present scenario the media has moved from the service industry to the money making industry. Many media organizations have lost their ethics and forgotten their social responsibility but there are a few exceptions. One such exception is Namma TV, a Kannada channel which is committed to benefit the society at large through its various programmes. This TV channel covers three districts like Dakshina Kannada, Udupi and Uttara Kannada in coastal Karnataka.

“Karunallu Ba Belake” (Lead kindly light) is one such program which is giving moral support and voice to the voiceless. This program is specially meant for victims, underprivileged people with disabilities and those who suffered terribly in their life due to some reasons and health related problems. This programme has been very successful and is well received by the viewers. In fact many of the viewers have come forward to provide financial assistance to the victims. This paper an attempt has been made to highlight the role of mass media in developmental issue and social responsibility of Namma TV through its various programmes and also highlighting feedback from the beneficiaries

IndexTerms - Media, Development, Social Responsibility

I.INTRODUCTION

In today's world mass media is playing an outstanding role in strengthening society. Mass media is a tremendous source of information for individuals as well as the society. The mass media like newspapers, radio and television acts as a bridge between the government and the people. Media is recognized as a powerful instrument to mould public opinion. Mass media is considered as the ‘fourth estate’ of democracy. Innovations of new communication technologies have immense power in the mass media. The mass media shapes viewers perceptions and views of social reality by presenting only some aspects of reality. The role of media is very crucial in an integral part of human life. Modern media world is regarded as “Window to the world”. It is well accepted that mass media has a definite role in the process of social change. The amount of the mass media’s involvement in welfare activities is enormous. The role and content of mass media has changed dramatically. If the media plays its role honestly, it will be a great force in building the nation. But unfortunately at present the media has become a commercialized sector for breaking news. Instead of giving useful information and educative programmes, channels present their news in a sensational format. Gaining Television Rating Points (TRP) has become one and only goal of media.

Social responsibility theory:

Mass media policies create social consciousness which is an essential factor to install an element of social responsibility among the people. Social responsibility was first used by the Robert Hutchins groups in a free and responsible press report in 1947 and nine years later in four theories of the press. “Proponents of social responsibility recognize that it is closely related to the libertarian press system, but they see it as going beyond the press theory, in that it places many moral and ethical restrictions on the press. Instead of emphasizing “freedom” it stresses “social responsibility” to the society of which it is a part. Social responsibility should be accurately and in a meaningful context.

Theories deal with the content and impact of media and society, the four theories of the press a duty to one’s conscience is the primary basis of the rights of free expression under social responsibility. According to social responsibility theory the media should be free but at the same time be socially responsible. The social responsibilities of the media include informing the public correctly about events and mould public opinion on every issue in a fair manner. This theory implies that the media has to combine responsibility with freedom on its own accord in keeping with the public good. (Balan, 1992)

Wilbur Schramm stresses these aspects of social communication which reflect the structure and development of society; size of communication reflects the economic development, the controls on communication reflects the political development, the content of communication at any given time reflects the value pattern of the society and the pattern of communication networks reflect the homogeneity of culture and geography of a society.

Social Obligation:

The term social welfare is very comprehensive in its meaning. It includes a large number of activities connected with the uplift and welfare of the weak and exploited sections of the society. Accordingly the term 'social responsibility refers to both social-economic and socio human obligation to others. Social change can be defined as a change in social structure. According to another definition "Social change is a deviation from the accepted modes of life".

Media and social responsibility:

Social responsibility is defined as the process by which a conglomerate participates in the welfare of the community, enhancing its environment and well-being to the advantages of the organization and the community concerned. Before independence print media was perceived as a mission only, because it was primarily oriented to the public interest. After independence the media developed as an occupation with primary emphasis on service to the public. On many occasions journalists have made strong claims of their observance of social responsibility.

The Indian Federation of Working Journalists in a declaration on 26th April 1971 declared that "the working journalists of India declare that the objectives of the profession of journalism are closely related to the wider social objectives to which the nation is pledged". The press has to function as an integral part of a just social order in which the people have a vital interest. Working journalists pledge themselves to maintain an integrated social outlook, keep in mind the larger interests of the people and work always with a sense of social responsibility. Similarly the National Union of Journalists in a declaration in February 1981 affirmed that the working journalists in India, considered as a trust, believe in serving the public interest by publishing news and comments in a free and fair manner. Journalists asserted their responsibility to the public and promised to discharge it faithfully. The importance of social responsibility has further increased because of the changing corporate world. (Sharma,1990)

Studies on Media responsibility:

It has been alleged that journalists neglect social interest. In 1973 Driberg said that the press does not exhibit social commitment. The press has not worked in accordance with the declarations made to the public. For this reason, the Indian public today has lost faith in the honesty of journalism. In 1972 Sarkar submits that the Indian public is largely unsympathetic to the press and is critical of its efficiency and performance. The allegation of neglecting social interests has been confirmed by various studies of newspaper's content, conducted by journalists and journalism organizations. Prasad holds that reporting on social change is one of the underdeveloped areas of our press. Agriculture, rural development, health, education and social welfare together at present receive less than a twentieth of newspaper space.

Sarkar says that the Press Institute of India found this charge to be true. Similar are the findings of the study undertaken recently by the Department of Communication and Journalism of Osmania University. Kamath states that the department analyzed the contents of eight major English newspapers in four regions in 1978. The study found that, on an average, only 9.05 % of space was devoted to 'social issues' which again included health, education, employment, crime, religion, marriage, dowry, language, prohibition, strikes and agitations. From the foregoing discussion it may be concluded that social interest has not been given due consideration in contemporary Indian journalism. (Sharma, 1990) Social effects of mass media in India is a critical assessment of the media scene including the findings of the first-ever country-wide survey of the social effects of the media, especially TV, conducted by the Center for Media Studies during 1994-95; and recommended future that includes in the case of Akashvani and Doordarshan.

Role of Television in Social Development:

Television of a country is the mirror for its national personality. Television must reflect the changing life pattern and problems of the basic social categories of Indian society. The media should reflect the extant social situation. Televisions aimed at dissemination development information and promote the process of modernization and encourage public participation and support in developmental programmes.

In 1975 Satellite instructional television experiment (SITE) program was successfully completed in 2330 villages in 20 districts of six states namely Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, Orissa and Rajasthan. Television exclusively used for development communication was the Kheda Communication Project (KCP) which demonstrated a new approach to use of television for development and education but also to try out a more meaningful direction for Indian Television, KCP succeeded in demonstrating effectively that TV could be used for development and social change. (Joshi, 2005)

Social Change Initiatives has been instituted for the purpose of promoting, encouraging and motivating excellence in reporting and covering social issues by TV news channels and it takes forward CMS's sustained initiatives towards incentivizing good practices and amplifying the positive power of the television news industry. The CMS (Center for media study) - The exchange4media News Broadcasting National Award for Social Change Initiatives 2012 was conferred to HMTV Telugu channel for its engaging and innovative programmes on gender issues in Andhra Pradesh.

Kannada TV Channels and Social Responsibility:

In Karnataka D.D. Chandana is a Kannada TV channel under Doordarshan available to more than 80% of the population of Karnataka. Udaya TV is the first Kannada entertainment channel, ETV Kannada, Zee Kannada, Asianet Suvarna and Kasthuri entertainment satellite channels airs different programs like soap opera, serials, reality shows, news, talk shows, game shows, health and live in programs. News channels such as TV9 Kannada, Suvarna News 24X7, Public TV, Republic TV, and Raj News, News 9 have wide range programs from hourly news, analysis of major news, events, panel discussion, Interviews and so on.

Apart from their routine of news telecast, many channels focused on developmental issues through their various programs. TV 9 Kannada has a tagline "A Better Society" and the channel is fighting against corruption. This channel took special initiative for Endosulfan victims in Dakshina Kannada through "Endosulfan Victims Welfare Fund". The channel received good response from the public through their charity.

In 2008 few parts of the north Karnataka districts affected by floods. On that time many print and electronic media voluntarily started "North India flood relief charity" for strengthen the victims. Even the public's supported a lot to rebuild the houses and the need of the village peoples. "Kolaku Belaku" is new program for the slum dwellers to showcase their talent hunt organized by Suvarna News 24x7 in 2012. Such programs were telecasted by many channels in all over the nation.

Profile of Dakshina Kannada

Dakshina Kannada - is a coastal district in the state of Karnataka in India. Today it is emerging as one of the important districts in the field of Education, Industrial sector, Banking sector, Medicare, Tourism, Rural development, Agricultural development, Cultural promotion and so on. Mangalore is the district headquarters of Dakshina Kannada, and has been a trading center for several centuries. The district is called the cradle of Indian banking. Over the years Dakshina Kannada has grown rapidly into a rich industrial zone.

Kannada Journalism began with the publication of "Mangaluru Samachara" by Herman Mogling in 1843 at the Basel Mission in Mangalore. More than 200 papers were published during the 1843-1973 period and most of the papers were weekly and monthly publications. In 1941 the first daily newspaper titled "Navabharatha" started by Vaman Srinivasa Kudva in Mangalore. In 1984 "Mungaru" newspaper started with an intention of social concern. At present most of the English and Kannada newspapers have Mangalore editions and are initiated for social causes.

It is now nearly three decades before Master Studio in Mangalore started producing programmes for TV viewers, starting from the news in Kannada under the City Cable brand. In the beginning the local programmes have large scope and miles to go to attain perfection. The arrival of technology made it easier and computer graphics, interfacing of computers with video consoles and many more advanced features add speed and accuracy to programming. Because of this effort done by a photographer today the city is buzzing with producers, both independent and corporate. There were only a few players in Mangalore in the local channel scene, namely the New Mangalore Channel, CCTV, OCN and CAD Television.

In the district the cable TV network runs local channels i.e. Namma Tv, V4 news, Namma Kudla, Coastal Times, Sahaya TV and Abbakka TV 24X7 are multilingual channels running successfully. This TV channel covers three districts like Dakshina Kannada, Udupi and Uttara Kannada in coastal Karnataka. All these channels will reach to help the people in large through their various programmes. Many media organizations have lost their ethics and forgotten their social responsibility but there are a few exceptions. One such exception is Namma TV.

Objectives of the study:

The study examines the role of mass media for development and social responsibility. The study is designed with the following objectives.

- To examine the social responsibility initiatives undertaken by media organizations.
- To analyze the key observations and themes of the "Karunallu Ba Belake" (Lead Kindly Light) program.
- To assess the impact of the program on its audience and society.
- To provide recommendations for enhancing the program's effectiveness and strengthening media organizations' social responsibility efforts.

Methodology:

The study is confined to Dakshina Kannada district, Karnataka. The present study is empirical research based on case study method. The data collected constitutes both primary and secondary type of data collection method.

Development and Social responsibility of Namma TV:

Namma Tv is a Kannada 24 hours a popular local news and entertainment television channel from Katalyst's Production Pvt Ltd., Mangalore. It was launched in February 2005. The news channel has been positioned as aggressive and focused on quality news. The tag line for Namma TV is 'Everything for everyone'. The channel is one of the most viewed channels in coastal Karnataka news service. The channel is also increasing social responsibility, public awareness. Namma TV is being transmitted by cable operators in coastal Karnataka from Kulai in Mangalore up to Karwar in Uttara Kannada district.

Namma TV a Kannada a popular local news and entertainment television channel which is committed to benefit the society at large through its various programmes. Namma TV is committed to benefit the society at large through its various programmes. Along with providing live news, 'Jana Dhvani'- live discussion program focused on a variety of social and development issues of the district. Through Tulu language program channel is trying to esteem the culture of Tulu Nadu. Apart from this the channel has other entertainment; live phone in programs, talk shows, youth, women, children, intelligence tests, musicals, live coverage, interviews, travelogues, current affairs, legal help, road shows, quiz, religious programs, cultural, dance and comedy shows.

"Karunalu Baa Belake" (Lead kindly light) is one such program which is giving moral support and voice to the voiceless. The program was started in 2008 and more than 150 episodes are telecasted weekly on Sunday at 2.30 p.m. This program is specially meant for victims, underprivileged people with disabilities and those who suffered terribly in their life due to some reasons and health related problems.

A girl from Bajpe (Mangalore airport) had severe accident injuries. She lost her two eye sights and failed one kidney. Her parents are very poor and working for daily wages. So they are not in a position to spend the money for her medical treatment. At that time through this programme Namma TV broadcasted one episode about her. At the same time other print and state level news channels also cover the same report as their social responsibility. Because of the media support her family received nine lacks rupees for her treatment.

An agriculturist from Belthangady taluk had spinal cord injury because of elephant stampede. His three small girl children discontinued their education. The family is not in position to manage their daily needs. After telecasting the program one person came forward with some offer to continue children's education.

This programme telecasted one special program related to a social worker Ramesh Shetty from Udupi. Till now he constructed eight free of cost houses for the homeless people. Even at present he is ready to give any kind of assistance for underprivileged people.

This program covered various health problems like hole in heart for 2 months and 8 months old baby, different types of cancers, liver problem, kidney failure, effect of polio, mental problem, handicapped people, severe injuries by accidents, blindness and fire related burns and so on.

This program is meant for all caste and religious people of the ruler area. The channel is mainly focusing on people of minor age rather than elder. After telecasting the program a well-known hospital in Mangalore came forward for free medical treatment. From the last five years this programme has been very successful and is well received by the viewers. In fact many of the viewers have come forward to provide financial assistance to the victims. The program covers all necessary information such as bank a/c, IFSC code, contact details and postal address for further communication. In some circumstances the victims received Rs 500 to 70,000 as a charity.

Few suggestions such program as follows:

- § The media house should encourage the team to follow up the story.
- § Regularly the channel should focus the impact of the episodes in their program
- § To have some tie-ups with NGO's for functioning better
- § Problems should be brought to the notice of local government and officers.

Even Namma TV had special programs on consumer's problems, environmental issues such as Endosulfan, Niddodi, Ethinahole project in Dakshina Kannada

Conclusion:

Quote the words of Justice Markandey Katju "the real problems of the Indian people are sidelined or treated as non-issues, and the non-issues are projected as if they are the real issues".

Mass media have both positive and negative roles in the public. The media should highlight the good deeds in society. There is an imperative need for every kind of mass media to shoulder the responsibility of removing social problems and taking the people towards change, progress and development. Thus mass media is playing an instrumental role in the social transition and development. Media should uphold the truth, integrity and be socially responsible. Social responsibility probably exists at the national level more than at local level. In India some media organizations are doing something for society, but what about others? The Ministry of Information and Broadcasting (MIB) should mandate social responsibility for media organizations. At the local level Namma TV did remarkable service to the voiceless people in Dakshina Kannada.

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